

Synthesis and characterization of spinel LiMn_2O_4 nanoparticles by urea assisted combustion synthesis

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Abstract : Spinel LiMn_2O_4 has been widely used as cathode material in lithium ion batteries because of its high energy density, low cost, high abundance, environmental friendliness etc. The application of LiMn_2O_4 in high power applications is limited by its low rate capability. In order to overcome this problem, attempts have made through the reduction of particle size from micro to nano scale. The nanosize materials not only increase the electrode-electrolyte surface contact area but also shortens the diffusion lengths of both electrons and lithium ions. Synthesis process plays a key role in developing various nanostructured materials. In the present work, nanocrystalline LiMn_2O_4 particles were prepared by urea assisted combustion process using citric acid and urea as fuels. Thermal behavior, phase analysis, structural co-ordination, surface morphology, specific surface area and electrical conductivity of prepared LiMn_2O_4 particles were studied through TG/DTA, XRD, FTIR, SEM, BET-surface area analysis and impedance spectroscopy measurements, respectively^{1,2}.

Keywords : Rechargeable lithium batteries, cathode material, LiMn_2O_4 , urea assisted combustion synthesis.

Introduction

Lithium battery offers the highest energy density among the available rechargeable batteries, dominating the market for mobile, laptop, i-Pod etc., for last two decades. In fact cathode material play main role in the determination of energy density, cycle life and safety of lithium battery. In recent year the transition metal oxides LiCoO_2 , LiNiO_2 , LiMn_2O_4 have been focus of considerable attention for lithium battery applications due to their high energy density and capacity. Among the cathode materials spinel LiMn_2O_4 is the promising material, because of its high theoretical energy density, high natural abundance, low cost and safety of lithium battery³.

Synthesis process play major role for preparation of cathode materials for lithium battery. Solid state reaction is the common method for the preparation nanocrystalline metal oxides. However, it is involve high temperature and long heat treatment time, hydrothermal, sol gel, combustion are the other wet chemical synthesis process have been used for preparation spinel nanocrystalline LiMn_2O_4 particles⁴. Among this combustion synthesis is the best method for the preparation nanocrystalline metal oxides.

Citric acid used as fuel as well as chelating agent in polymeric citrate route, is one of the combustion synthesis process. Disadvanges of this process is the exhibit impurity phase. In order to overcome these disadvantages, the prepared powder sintered at high temperatures, which cause in bigger crystalline size. New combustion synthesis, urea with citric acid used as a fuels in the presence of nitric acid, which decrease the ignition temperature and yield pure organic free nanocrystalline oxide powder.

Results and discussion

Thermal analysis of polymeric intermediate LiMn_2O_4 sample by TG/DTA :

The thermogram of polymeric intermediate of LiMn_2O_4 sample prepared by urea assisted combustion synthesis shown in Fig. 1. The exothermic peak observed at 220 °C and the corresponding weight loss about 40% is due to the combustion of polymeric intermediated. The weight loss about 11% between the temperatures 370 °C and 390 °C is due to the decomposition of organic compounds. No more weight loss observed after 600 °C, it confirm the absolute decomposition of organic residues as well as

Fig. 1. TG/DTA thermograms of polymeric intermediate of LiMn_2O_4 sample.

the complete formation LiMn_2O_4 compound. Hence $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is optimized as the complete formation of LiMn_2O_4 , further it is supported by XRD and FTIR results.

XRD :

Fig. 2 shows the XRD pattern of as-prepared and calcined LiMn_2O_4 sample. X-Ray diffraction of polymeric intermediate of LiMn_2O_4 does not show any peaks, it indicate that polymeric intermediate may be amorphous in nature and pure crystalline phase was obtained at $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Formation of LiMn_2O_4 phase was confirmed by comparing their respective XRD pattern of standard JCPDS and these result supported by TG/DTA results and further supported by FTIR results.

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of as-prepared and calcined LiMn_2O_4 sample along with JCPDS data.

FTIR :

Fig. 3 shows the FTIR spectra of the LiMn_2O_4 sample at different temperature. From Fig. 3 the observed IR

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of as-prepared and calcined LiMn_2O_4 sample.

peaks at 1725 cm^{-1} and 1389 cm^{-1} are corresponds to the asymmetric and symmetric vibrations of COO^- group respectively. The observed band at 612 cm^{-1} and 510 cm^{-1} , which are assigned to the O-Mn-O vibrations^{5,6}, indicate the formation of LiMn_2O_4 structure and further it was consisted by XRD analysis.

SEM :

Fig. 4(a) shows the SEM images of pure LiMn_2O_4 nanoparticles with high agglomeration were observed. The particle size of LiMn_2O_4 is found to be $< 350\text{ nm}$. From Fig. 3(b) shows the confirmation of pure LiMn_2O_4 nanoparticles without organic contamination.

BET surface area analysis :

Fig. 5 shows the nitrogen adsorption isotherm of LiMn_2O_4 nanoparticles were obtained with NOVA 3200e (Quantum chrome instrument-USA) Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface analyzer. BET calculations of specific surface area of LiMn_2O_4 nanoparticles are found to be $126.013\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ ^{7,8}.

Electrical conductivity :

Fig. 6 shows the impedance plot of LiMn_2O_4 nanoparticles obtained at 300 K . The impedance plot is fitted using win fit software by adjusting the resistance and capacitance values. The observed semicircle is represents the parallel combination resistive and capacitive elements of the sample. The conductivity of LiMn_2O_4 sample was calculated using bulk resistance (R_B) and dimension of the pellets. The total conductivity of the LiMn_2O_4 is found to be $2.677 \times 10^{-5}\text{ S cm}^{-1}$.

Fig. 4(a). SEM images of LiMn_2O_4 sample.

Table 1. Concentration of elements present in the LiMn_2O_4 nanoparticles

Element line	Net counts	Net counts error	Weight (%)	Atom (%)	Formula
OK	2238	+/- 96	4113	70.53	O
MnK	1789	+/- 68	5887	29.42	Mn
MnL	869	+/- 93	-	-	
Total			100.00	100.00	

Experimental

Synthesis of nanocrystalline LiMn_2O_4 powder by combustion process :

$\text{CH}_3(\text{COO})_2\text{Mn}$ (SQ, Qualigens), LiNO_3 (AR, Loba

Fig. 4(b). SEM-EDX spectrum of LiMn_2O_4 sample.

Fig. 5. Nitrogen gas sorption at 78 K for LiMn_2O_4 nanoparticles.

Fig. 6. Impedance plots (Z' and Z'') of LiMn_2O_4 nanoparticles.

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Chemic), urea (SQ, Qualigens) and citric acid (SQ, Qualigens) are used for the synthesis of LiMn_2O_4 powder by urea assisted citrate process. Stoichiometric amounts of lithium nitrate and manganese acetate solutions were mixed with aqueous urea and citric acid in the ratio of 1 : 1. Concentrated nitric acid was mixed to the starting solution in the volume ratio of 1 : 5. Resulting solutions were evaporated at 80 °C for 4 to 6 h under continuous stirring and turned into resin, resulting resin was dried at 170 °C for 24 h. Further, it was calcined at 700 °C temperatures to get LiMn_2O_4 nanoparticles.

Conclusion

From XRD, FTIR, TG/DTA and SEM results confirmed the formation nanocrystalline pure LiMn_2O_4 particles prepared urea assisted combustion synthesis. The surface area of LiMn_2O_4 were calculated by using NOVA 3200e (Quantum chrome instrument-USA) BET surface analyzer and found to be 126.013 m^2/g . The electronic conductivity of LiMn_2O_4 sample were calculated by using NOVACONTROL impedance analyzer and electrical

conductivity of LiMn_2O_4 sample was found to be $2.677 \times 10^{-5} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$.

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